

Study of Non-Traumatic Causes of Acute Abdomen with the Aid of Advanced Radiological Imaging for the Early ManagementPriya Roy¹, Sanjay Singhal², Saroj Chhabra Kapoor³¹Post Graduate-3rd year, General Surgery, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Jaipur²Professor and H.O.D, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Jaipur³Professor, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Jaipur

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Abstract:

Introduction: The term 'acute abdomen' describes the abrupt onset of severe abdominal pain and tenderness, typically requiring immediate medical evaluation and often necessitating emergency surgical intervention. The abdomen is often likened to Pandora's box due to the potential for unforeseen discoveries during surgical exploration. Consequently, laparotomy, or surgical opening of the abdomen, is sometimes the final recourse for diagnosing abdominal conditions accurately. We highlight the importance of clinical examination in forming a preliminary diagnosis, the role of ultrasound, CT in refining differential diagnoses, and the planning of appropriate surgical treatments.

Aim: To study the non-traumatic causes of acute abdomen with the aid of advanced radiological imaging for the early management.

Objectives: a) To study about non-traumatic causes of acute abdomen in defined age groups. b) To study the aid of Radiological diagnostic tools i.e. X ray, Ultrasonography, CT scan in the diagnosis and management of the emergencies. c) To study about the mode of management of non-traumatic acute abdomen.

Methods: A Randomised prospective study was conducted at the Department of General Surgery, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Jaipur. It included all the patients of defined age group (18 to 65years) presenting to OPD and Emergency department with non-traumatic acute abdomen between September 2022 to March 2024.

Conclusion: The acute abdomen is frequently encountered as a surgical emergency, presenting a significant clinical challenge for surgeons. Acute abdomen predominantly afflicts males, occurring 1.5 times more often than in females. Acute appendicitis stands out as the leading cause of acute abdomen. Perforations most commonly occur in the small bowel, particularly in the duodenum. Obstructed hernias are the most frequent cause of intestinal obstruction. CT abdomen plays a critical role in diagnosing acute abdomen, especially when other methods fail to yield a definitive preoperative diagnosis, ensuring prompt patient management. Surgical intervention remains the cornerstone of management for the majority of patients.

Keywords: Acute abdomen, Appendicitis, Perforation, Usg, CT.

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Introduction

The term 'acute abdomen' describes the abrupt onset of severe abdominal pain and tenderness, typically requiring immediate medical evaluation and often necessitating emergency surgical intervention. This condition encompasses a diverse spectrum of surgical, medical, and gynaecological emergencies, ranging from less severe ailments to potentially life-threatening scenarios. Given its complexity, a thorough and rapid diagnostic process is essential to determine if surgery is necessary and to initiate appropriate treatment promptly. [1] Acute abdomen is a significant concern in emergency medicine, accounting for approximately 5-10% of all emergency visits. It stands as the most common surgical emergency and is a leading rea-

son for surgical consultations and non-accidental hospital admissions. Acute abdomen typically presents suddenly and can persist for several hours to days, accompanied by a diverse range of clinical features specific to the underlying cause. It remains a leading cause of mortality and morbidity within emergency departments. [2] Historically, Cope remarked in 1921 that severe abdominal pain lasting over six hours in previously healthy individuals usually signifies a condition of surgical importance. The effective management of acute abdomen hinges significantly on early diagnosis, prompt intervention, and comprehensive postoperative care. Sir Henle's aphorism underscores that in acute abdominal emergencies, the timing of surgery is more

critical than the specific surgical technique employed. Therefore, early intervention is paramount to achieving favourable outcomes in these urgent medical scenarios. [3,4] Acute abdominal pain is a common reason for hospital visits and impacts a broad demographic spectrum. [5] A comprehensive patient history and meticulous physical examination are indispensable tools in diagnosing gastrointestinal diseases and understanding abdominal pain. [9] Evaluating a patient with acute abdomen involves making a critical decision about whether to proceed with surgery, which typically requires general anaesthesia. This decision is guided by an evaluation of the patient's medical history, detailed physical examination findings, comprehensive laboratory tests, and diagnostic imaging studies. It is imperative that all patients presenting with abdominal pain undergo a rigorous evaluation to establish an accurate diagnosis, facilitating timely treatment aimed at minimizing complications and improving patient outcomes. The abdomen is often likened to Pandora's box due to the potential for unforeseen discoveries during surgical exploration. Consequently, laparotomy, or surgical opening of the abdomen, is sometimes the final recourse for diagnosing abdominal conditions accurately. [7]

In this study, we investigate the various clinical presentations of non-traumatic acute abdominal pain. We highlight the importance of clinical examination in forming a preliminary diagnosis, the role of ultrasound in refining differential diagnoses, and the planning of appropriate surgical treatments. Additionally, we examine the outcomes of these interventions to provide a comprehensive understanding of managing acute abdomen.

Aim and Objectives

Aim: To study the non-traumatic causes of acute abdomen with the aid of advanced radiological imaging for the early management.

Objectives:

- To study about non-traumatic causes of acute abdomen in defined age groups.
- To study the aid of Radiological diagnostic tools i.e. X ray, Ultrasonography, CT scan in the diagnosis and management of the emergencies.
- To study about the mode of management of non-traumatic acute abdomen.

Materials and Methods

This study was conducted at the Department of General Surgery, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Jaipur. It included all the patients of defined age group presenting with non-traumatic acute abdomen to OPD and Emergency department. Patients were selected through convenient sampling. Approval for the study was obtained from the Institute Ethics Committee of Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Jaipur.

Type of Study: Hospital Based prospective study

Place of Study: Department of General Surgery, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Jaipur

Period of Study: September 2022 to March 2024

Sample Size: All patients aged between 18 and 65 presenting with non-traumatic acute abdomen at the Outpatient Department (OPD) and Emergency Department of Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital

Selection Criteria:

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patient willing to give informed consent.
- Age between 18 and 65 years of either sex presenting with non-traumatic acute abdomen.
- Non-traumatic acute abdomen cases undergoing radiological investigations.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients presenting with traumatic acute abdomen.
- Pregnant women

Methodology:

Patients aged 18 to 65 presenting with non-traumatic acute abdomen at the outpatient or emergency department were included in this study.

- Informed written consent was obtained from all participants.
- Upon admission, all patients underwent detailed history taking to establish a pre-operative diagnosis, focusing on symptoms and duration of complaints.
- A comprehensive general physical and systemic examination was conducted.

Routine and radiological investigations necessary for preoperative evaluation were performed.

Results

Table 1: Age categorization of the Participants

Age in years	No. of patients	%
≤ 20	6	6.32%
21-30	22	23.16%
31-40	27	28.42%
41-50	19	20.00%
51-60	10	10.53%

> 60	11	11.58%
Total	95	100%
Mean age	39.67±13.509	

In our study of 95 patients, the age distribution was as follows: the largest cohort, accounting for 28.42% of the patients, was aged 31-40 years. The next largest group comprised 23.16% in the 21-30 years age bracket, followed by 20% in the 41-50 years age range. Patients over 60 years old constituted 11.58%, those aged 51-60 years were 10.53%, and individuals aged 20 years or younger made up 6.32% of the total.

Table 2: Gender categorization of the Participants

Gender	No. of patients	%
Male	59	62.1%
Female	36	37.9%
Total	95	100%

In our study, 62.1% of the participants were male, and 37.9% were female.

Table 3: Symptomatic profile of the Participants

Symptoms	Gender		Total
	Male (n=59)	Female (n=36)	
Only Pain	2 (3.4%)	2 (5.6%)	4 (4.2%)
Pain with Distension	13 (22.0%)	7 (19.4%)	20 (21.1%)
Pain with Fever	3 (5.1%)	1 (2.8%)	4 (4.2%)
Pain with Jaundice	2 (3.4%)	1 (2.8%)	4 (4.2%)
Pain with Vomiting	9 (15.3%)	15 (41.7%)	24 (25.3%)
Pain with Vomiting and Fever	13 (22.0%)	1 (2.8%)	14 (14.7%)
Pain with Vomiting and Distension	10 (16.9%)	8 (22.2%)	18 (18.9%)
Pain with Vomiting, Distension and Obstipation	7 (11.9%)	1 (2.8%)	8 (8.4%)

P=0.037, significant, Chi-Square test

In our study, all patients experienced pain as a primary symptom. The most frequent presentations were pain with vomiting (25.3%). 2nd most common presentation was of pain with distension (21.1%) followed by Pain with Vomiting and Distension(18.9%), Pain with Vomiting and Fever (14.7%), Pain with Jaundice (14.7%). There was no statistically significant difference observed between genders (P<0.05; P=0.037).

Table 4: Clinical findings among the Participants

Signs	Gender		Total
	Male (n=59)	Female (n=36)	
Nil	18 (30.5%)	13 (36.1%)	31 (32.6%)
Yes	41 (69.5%)	23 (63.9%)	64 (67.4%)
• Guarding/rigidity	31 (52.5%)	15 (41.7%)	46 (48.4%)
• Obstructed inguinal hernia	2 (3.4%)	1 (2.8%)	3 (3.2%)
• Obstructed umbilical hernia	8 (13.6%)	6 (16.7%)	14 (14.7%)
• Strangulated inguinal hernia	0 (0.0%)	1 (2.8%)	1 (1.1%)

P=0.026, Significant, $\chi^2 = 13.475$

In our study, 32.6% did not present with specific abdominal signs for clinical diagnosis. Among the remaining 67.4%, 48.4% exhibited guarding and rigidity, suggestive of hollow viscus perforation, 14.7% had symptoms of obstructed umbilical

hernia, 3.2% presented with obstructed inguinal hernia, 1.1% showed signs of strangulated inguinal hernia. There was no statistically significant difference observed between genders (P<0.05; P=0.026)."

Table 5: X-Ray interpretations among the Participants

X-Ray	Gender		Total
	Male (n=59)	Female (n=36)	
Normal	26 (44.1%)	19 (52.8%)	45 (47.4%)
Abnormal	33 (55.9%)	17 (47.2%)	50 (52.6%)
• Gas under the diaphragm	8 (13.6%)	7 (19.4%)	15 (15.8%)
• Multiple air fluids	13 (22%)	5 (13.9%)	18 (18.9%)
• Dilated bowel loops	3 (5.1%)	1 (2.8%)	4 (4.2%)

• Obstruction	7 (11.9%)	4 (11.1%)	11 (11.6%)
• Volvulus	2 (3.4%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (2.1%)

P=0.678, Not Significant, $\chi^2 = 3.145$

X-ray of the erect abdomen was routinely performed in all patients with acute abdomen. Results showed normal findings in 47.4% of cases. Among the remaining 52.6%, findings included gas under the diaphragm (15.8%), multiple air-fluid levels suggestive of hollow viscus perforation (18.9%),

and dilated bowel loops (4.2%). Features indicative of intestinal obstruction were noted in 11.6%, while 2.1% exhibited signs of volvulus.

There was no statistically significant difference observed between genders ($P>0.05$; $P=0.678$).

Table 6: USG interpretations among the Participants

USG	Gender		Total
	Male (n=59)	Female (n=36)	
Normal	2 (3.4%)	4 (11.1%)	6 (6.3%)
Abnormal	57 (96.6%)	32 (88.9%)	89 (93.7%)
• Acute Appendicitis	18 (30.5%)	7 (19.4%)	25 (26.3%)
• Intestinal obstruction	7 (10.2%)	1 (2.8%)	8 (7.4%)
• Appendicular lump	0 (0.0%)	2 (5.6%)	2 (2.1%)
• Calculus	3 (5.1%)	1 (2.8%)	4 (4.2%)
• Colitis with peritonitis	2 (3.4%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (2.1%)
• Dilated bowel loops	7 (11.9%)	5 (13.9%)	12 (12.6%)
• Diverticulitis	3 (5.1%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (3.2%)
• Empyema gall bladder	1 (1.7%)	4 (11.1%)	5 (5.3%)
• Gall stone induced pancreatitis	1 (1.7%)	4 (11.1%)	5 (5.3%)
• Intestinal perforation	1 (1.7%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (1.1%)
• Liver abscess	3 (5.1%)	1 (2.8%)	4 (4.2%)
• Meckel's diverticulum	0 (0.0%)	1 (2.8%)	1 (1.1%)
• Strangulated hernia	5 (6.1%)	2 (3.2%)	7 (6.8%)
• Viable	4 (6.8%)	5 (13.9%)	9 (9.5%)
• Volvulus	2 (3.4%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (2.1%)

P=0.135, Significant, $\chi^2 = 23.463$

Routine ultrasonography for acute surgical abdomen yielded normal results in 6.3% of patients. Remaining 93.7% showed positive findings i.e., maximum 26.3% had acute appendicitis, 7.4% had intestinal obstruction, 2.1% had appendicular lump, 4.2% had calculus, 2.1% had colitis with peritonitis, 12.6% had dilated bowel loops, 3.2% had diver-

ticulitis, 5.3% had empyema gall bladder, 5.3% had gall stone induced pancreatitis, 1.1% had intestinal perforation, 4.2% had liver abscess, 1.1% had Meckel's diverticulum, 6.8% had strangulated, 9.5% had viable and 2.1% had volvulus. There was no statistically significant difference observed between genders ($P>0.05$; $P=0.135$).

Table 7: CT interpretations among the Participants

CT	Gender		Total
	Male (n=59)	Female (n=36)	
Not done	35 (59.3%)	27 (75%)	62 (65.3%)
Abnormal	24 (40.7%)	9 (25%)	33 (34.7%)
• Acute appendicitis	3 (5.1%)	1 (2.8%)	4 (4.2%)
• Appendicular Lump	0 (0.0%)	2 (5.6%)	2 (2.1%)
• Dilatation of jejunal and proximal	2 (3.4%)	2 (5.6%)	4 (4.2%)
• Diverticulitis	3 (5.1%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (3.2%)
• Koch's abdomen	3 (5.1%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (3.2%)
• Liver abscess with contained perforation	3 (5.1%)	1 (2.8%)	4 (4.2%)
• Retrocecal appendicitis	3 (5.1%)	2 (5.6%)	5 (5.3%)
• Obstruction	5 (8.5%)	1 (2.8%)	6 (6.3%)
• Sigmoid volvulus	2 (3.4%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (2.1%)

P=0.278, Not Significant, $\chi^2 = 10.974$

CT abdomen was conducted in 34.7% of cases where diagnostic uncertainty persisted after other

investigations. Among these cases, CT scan confirmed acute appendicitis in 4.2% of patients, ap-

pendicular lump in 2.1%, jejuna and proximal dilation in 4.2%, diverticulitis in 3.2%, Koch's abdomen in 3.2%, liver abscess with contained perforation in 4.2%, retrocecal appendicitis in 5.2%, intes-

tinal obstruction in 6.3% and sigmoid volvulus in 2.1% patients. There was no statistically significant difference observed between genders ($P>0.05$; $P=0.278$).

Table 8: Surgical observations

Intra-op Findings	Gender		Total
	Male (n=59)	Female (n=36)	
Nil	8 (13.6%)	7 (19.4%)	15 (15.8%)
Acute Appendicitis	15 (25.4%)	4 (11.1%)	19 (20.0%)
Appendicolith	1 (1.7%)	2 (5.6%)	3 (3.2%)
Empyema gall bladder	1 (1.7%)	4 (11.1%)	5 (5.3%)
Ileal perforation	4 (6.8%)	6 (16.7%)	10 (10.5%)
Large bowel obstruction	4 (6.8%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (4.2%)
Meckel's diverticulum	0 (0.0%)	2 (5.6%)	2 (2.1%)
Peptic perforation	5 (5.1%)	1 (2.8%)	6 (4.2%)
Retrocecal appendicitis	2 (3.4%)	1 (2.8%)	3 (3.2%)
Sigmoid volvulus	2 (3.4%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (2.1%)
Small bowel obstruction	6 (6.8%)	2 (5.6%)	8 (8.3%)
Strangulated Hernia	4 (5.1%)	2 (2.8%)	6 (5.6%)
TB abdomen	3 (5.1%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (3.2%)
Obstructed Hernia	4 (6.8%)	5 (11.1%)	9 (9.1%)

$P=0.070$, Not Significant, $\chi^2 = 26.273$

The correlation between CT abdomen findings and laparotomy revealed various pathologies: intestinal obstruction due to adhesions, intussusception, Meckel's diverticulum-related pathology, diverticulitis, tuberculosis causing abdominal obstruction, and retrocecal appendix in case of appendicitis. These findings were consistent between CT scan and surgical exploration.

Table 9: Proportion of different surgical procedures

Type of surgery performed	Gender		Total
	Male (n=59)	Female (n=36)	
Exploratory laparotomy	32 (54.2%)	18 (50.0%)	50 (52.6%)
Laparoscopic Appendectomy	6 (10.2%)	1 (2.8%)	7 (7.4%)
Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy	1 (1.7%)	4 (11.1%)	5 (5.3%)
Open Appendectomy	16 (27.1%)	8 (22.2%)	24 (25.3%)
Mesh Hernioplasty	4 (6.8%)	5 (13.9%)	9 (9.5%)

$P=0.141$, Not Significant, $\chi^2 = 6.906$

Most common surgical procedures were done with exploratory laparotomy with Graham's omentoplasty for perforative peritonitis and ileostomy for intestinal obstruction followed by laparoscopic/open appendectomy for acute appendicitis. There was no statistically significant difference observed between genders ($P>0.05$; $P=0.141$).

Table 10: Drain placement in the Participants

Drain	Gender		Total
	Male (n=59)	Female (n=36)	
Yes	33 (55.9%)	22 (61.1%)	55 (57.9%)
No	26 (44.1%)	14 (38.9%)	40 (42.1%)

$P=0.620$, Not Significant, $\chi^2 = 0.246$

The study investigated the role of drain placement in reducing morbidity and promoting faster recovery. Drain placement was implemented in 57.9% of cases. There was no statistically significant difference observed between genders ($P>0.05$; $P=0.620$).

Table 11: Blood transfusion in the Participants

Blood	Gender	Total
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	Male (n=59)	Female (n=36)	
Not used	51 (86.4%)	34 (94.4%)	85 (89.5%)
Used	8 (13.6%)	2 (5.6%)	10 (10.5%)
1 pint	5 (8.5%)	2 (5.6%)	7 (7.4%)
2 pints	3 (5.1%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (3.2%)

P=0.325, Not Significant, $\chi^2 = 2.249$

- The study on blood usage and necessity in laparotomies revealed the following findings:
- 10.5% of cases required blood transfusion.
- Specifically, 7.4% of cases received 1 pint of blood transfusion.
- Furthermore, 3.2% of cases received 2 pints of blood transfusion.
- There was no statistically significant difference observed between genders ($P>0.05$; $P=0.182$).

Table 12: Discharge outcomes

Discharge	Gender		Total
	Male (n=59)	Female (n=36)	
2 days	21 (35.6%)	11 (30.6%)	32 (33.7%)
3 days	12 (20.3%)	8 (22.2%)	20 (21.1%)
4 days	12 (20.3%)	6 (16.7%)	18 (18.9%)
5 days	12 (20.3%)	11 (30.6%)	23 (24.2%)
6 days	2 (3.4%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (2.1%)
Mean	3.40±1.241		

P=0.636, Not Significant, $\chi^2 = 2.549$

- The distribution of hospital stays for patients is as follows:
- The largest group, comprising 33.7% of patients, recovered uneventfully and were discharged within 2 days.
- 24.2% of patients were discharged within 5 days.
- 21.1% had a hospital stay of 3 days.
- 18.9% were discharged within 4 days.
- A smaller percentage, 2.1%, required a hospital stay of 6 days.
- On average, patients stayed in the hospital for 3.40 day. There was no statistically significant difference observed between genders ($P>0.05$; $P=0.636$).

Table 13: Mode of Management

Mode of Management	No. of patients	Percentage
Conservative	27	28.42%
Surgery	68	71.58%
Total	95	100%

The table above indicates that the majority of patients accounting for 71.58%, underwent surgical management, while 28.42% were managed conservatively.

Discussion

Acute abdominal pain is a frequent cause of admissions in general surgical emergencies characterized by a wide spectrum of differential diagnosis that pose significant challenges to surgeons. This study specifically investigated non-traumatic acute abdominal pain, which predominantly affected patients aged between their 2nd and 5th decades, with a mean age of 39.67 ± 13.509 years. The highest incidence was observed in individuals in their third decade of life. Regarding gender distribution: Perforated duodenal ulcers showed a male-to-female ratio of 3:2, consistent with findings from Stainland et al.⁸ Acute appendicitis exhibited a male-to-female ratio of 2:1, aligning closely with ratios

reported in studies by Stainland et al. [8] (1:1.5) and Iqbal et al. [9] (1:3.7). The third decade emerged as the most common age group affected by acute appendicitis in both males and females. These findings underscore the demographic patterns and gender discrepancies in non-traumatic acute abdominal conditions, providing crucial insights for clinical management and further research. These findings highlight the demographic patterns and gender differences in the occurrence of acute abdominal conditions, providing valuable insights for clinical management and further research. A comparison of clinical presentations across different studies highlights common symptoms. In a study by Kesarwani A et al. [10], abdominal pain was reported by all patients, followed by vomiting (78%), abdominal distension (26%), and fever (17%). Barai B et al. [11] found similar patterns: abdominal pain in all patients (100%), vomiting in 42%, abdominal distension in 22.13%,

and fever in 4%. In our study, abdominal pain was the primary complaint in all 50 patients (100%), followed by vomiting (67.3%), abdominal distension (48.4%), and fever (18.9%). The high incidence of vomiting indicates that many patients exhibited features of systemic inflammatory response syndrome upon arrival, potentially due to illiteracy and delays in seeking medical treatment in the study area.

In a developing country such as India, the spectrum of diseases presenting as non-traumatic acute abdomen differs significantly from those seen in developed countries. For instance, a study conducted in Boston, Massachusetts, USA, highlighted urinary tract calculi (31.4%), acute appendicitis (23.6%), intraperitoneal abscess (17.4%), diverticulitis (16.9%), and acute small intestinal obstruction (10.6%) as the most common causes. In contrast, studies from sub-Saharan Africa identified small bowel obstruction, acute appendicitis, typhoid ileal perforation, and perforated peptic ulcer [10,12-15] as leading causes.

Similarly, research from India, such as that by Jain et al. [74], reported perforative peritonitis (39.7%), acute appendicitis (37.7%), and intestinal obstruction (14.2%) as predominant. Likewise, studies by Ray et al. [17] also highlighted perforative peritonitis as a primary reason for surgical intervention in acute abdominal pain cases.

In Ethiopia, Hagos et al. [18] found acute appendicitis (53.2%) and bowel obstruction (28.7%) to be the main causes, with perforative peritonitis (4.3%) following. In our current study, acute appendicitis emerged as the most frequent cause of acute abdomen (28.4%), followed by bowel obstruction (19%) and intestinal obstruction (7.4%), consistent with findings from other studies in India. Additionally, emergency abdominal surgery in our study was most commonly performed in individuals aged 20 to 60 years. In this study, emergency abdominal surgery was most frequently performed in individuals aged 20 to 60 years.

However, the reasons for surgery varied across different age groups. Among younger patients, those in their 20s and 30s, acute appendicitis was the most common indication for surgery. In contrast, for older patients, those in their 50s to 70s, intestinal obstruction and bowel loops were more prevalent surgical indications. Most patients diagnosed with perforative peritonitis presented to the emergency department with an average history of three days of abdominal pain. On arrival, they exhibited classic signs of peritonitis, such as abdominal guarding and rigidity. These symptoms indicate inflammation of the peritoneum, typically characterized by severe pain and tenderness in the abdomen, often accompanied by muscle tightness. Intraoperatively, patients with gastric and duodenal

perforations underwent a procedure known as Graham's omentoplasty. This technique involves using a part of the omentum, a layer of fatty tissue that drapes over the abdominal organs, to cover and close the perforation site. The omentum is stitched over the perforation to reinforce the closure and promote healing. For cases of intestinal obstruction, the causes varied. The most common cause was obstructed ventral hernias. These hernias occur when a portion of the intestine protrudes through a weakness in the abdominal wall, leading to obstruction. The next most frequent cause was adhesions, which are bands of scar tissue that can form after surgery or inflammation and can cause the intestines to stick together, leading to blockage.

Other causes included tubercular strictures, which are narrowing of the intestines due to tuberculosis infection, and volvulus, a condition where a loop of the intestine twists around itself and the mesentery that supports it, causing an obstruction. Additionally, malignant growths, such as tumors, can cause luminal obstruction by physically blocking the passage of intestinal contents. Each of these conditions requires specific surgical interventions to relieve the obstruction and address the underlying cause. The approach to treatment is tailored to the individual patient's condition and the specific cause of their intestinal obstruction.

In this study, acute appendicitis emerged as the most prevalent cause of acute abdominal conditions, resulting in generally positive outcomes for the majority of patients. The rate of major postoperative complications was low.

Specifically, 1.05% of patients experienced complications necessitating pig tail catheterization, a procedure used to drain abscesses or other fluid collections, and 2.1% required the Ochsner Sherren regimen, which involves conservative management of intra-abdominal abscesses following laparotomies. A significant portion of patients, 64.2%, were able to be discharged within 3-5 days after surgery, having made an uneventful recovery without further complications.

However, higher mortality rates were observed among patients suffering from intestinal perforation and malignant intestinal obstruction. These conditions are more severe and carry higher risks due to factors such as the spread of infection and the complexity of the surgeries required. Comparative studies offer valuable insights into varying outcomes. For example, Chavan et al. [19] focused exclusively on elderly patients and reported a strikingly higher mortality rate of 17%. This elevated rate can be attributed to age-related vulnerabilities such as increased susceptibility to infections and reduced wound healing capacity compared to younger individuals. In contrast, Barai et al. [11] documented a markedly lower mortality rate of 1.72%. This dif-

ference may be explained by the study's inclusion of fewer complex cases necessitating surgical intervention, thereby mitigating the overall risk of unfavorable outcomes. The variation in mortality rates across different studies highlights the influence of several critical factors: the specific type of pathology being treated, the age group of the patients, and the presence of co-morbidities. In this study, while the mortality rate was slightly higher than that reported by Barai et al. [11], it remained lower compared to the rates documented in studies conducted by Chavan et al. [19] and Ray et al. [17]. This suggests that while the outcomes for acute appendicitis were generally favorable, more severe conditions like intestinal perforation and malignant obstructions continue to pose significant risks, particularly in older populations or those with additional health complications.

Conclusion

- The acute abdomen is frequently encountered as a surgical emergency, presenting a significant clinical challenge for surgeons.
 - Acute abdomen predominantly afflicts males, occurring 1.5 times more often than in females.
 - This condition is most prevalent in individuals under 40 years old, with its incidence declining beyond this age.
 - Acute appendicitis stands out as the leading cause of acute abdomen.
 - It primarily affects younger adults, with the highest occurrence among those aged 21-40 years.
 - Key clinical manifestations of acute appendicitis include pain, fever, and vomiting.
 - Perforations most commonly occur in the small bowel, particularly in the duodenum.
 - Peptic ulcer disease is the leading cause of perforations in both the duodenum and the stomach.
 - Obstructed hernias are the most frequent cause of intestinal obstruction.
 - Significant advances in radiological diagnostics such as ultrasound (USG) and CT scan have transformed the diagnosis of acute abdomen.
 - CT abdomen plays a critical role in diagnosing acute abdomen, especially when other methods fail to yield a definitive preoperative diagnosis, ensuring prompt patient management.
 - An upright abdominal X-ray remains essential for evaluating multiple air-fluid levels.
 - Surgical intervention remains the cornerstone of management for the majority of patients.
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